

Research

Ink – Traditional Medium, Techniques and Latest Experiments in Chinese Contemporary Art

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***Abstract:** This research paper primarily focuses on the analytical study of the diverse genres of Chinese contemporary ink art. Chinese contemporary ink art originated from the '85 New Wave Art Movement, flourished in the 1990s, and matured in the 21st century. Over the past 30 years, a large number of ink and wash artists have carried out various experiments and explorations from the expansion of the new ink language and the innovation of artistic creation themes. At the same time, a group of art critics has also done theoretical writing, curated exhibitions, and academic seminars. Contemporary ink and wash painting conformed to the trend of contemporary social development and expresses the contemporary thinking of people in contemporary society. Western contemporary art, industrialization, and globalization have had a profound impact on the development of Chinese ink painting, and ink painting has also influenced the world painting through internationalization. Appropriate to the introduction of western painting concepts and theories, the theories and concepts of Chinese ink painting have undergone fundamental changes, several techniques of western art are combined with traditional ink and wash techniques, Chinese ink painting adapted to the new aesthetic and visual forms of contemporary art. Nowadays Chinese contemporary art has a great cultural dilemma. Does it only signify Chinese culture or international global culture? This research paper focuses on the analysis, combing, and summarizing of the diversified phenomenon of Chinese contemporary ink and wash painting during the contemporary stage.*

Keywords: Chinese, Ink Art, Contemporary Art, Genre, Aesthetics

1. Introduction

1.1 Development of Chinese Contemporary Ink Art

Ink art is an exceptional tradition of Chinese culture, which contains and continues the 5,000-year-old ideological spirit of Chinese civilization. Traditional ink painting refers to the continuation of traditional Chinese ink painting. Its value ideal and aesthetic interest is all based on classical Chinese painting. Ink is not only representing a medium, but it is also a philosophy of Chinese tradition. The development of Chinese contemporary art over the past 30 years has reshaped the relationship between Guohua (Chinese-style painting) and Xihua (Western-style painting) in two fundamental ways. *First*, to a group of ink painters, the issue at stake is no longer how to westernize Guohua, but how to make it contemporary and global. *Second*, the proliferation of modern and contemporary art in the 1980s and 1990s had the effect of dismantling the medium-based division between Guohua and Xihua. This is because, compared with ink and oil painting, newly introduced contemporary art forms installation, performance, site-specific art, multimedia art, body art, etc. are not strictly culture-specific. The first focus is a new type of ink painting that transformed Guohua from within. It has been termed variously as Modern ink painting (Xiandai Shuimo), Experimental ink painting (Shiyan Shuimo), Conceptual ink painting (Guannian Shuimo), or simply New Chinese-style painting (Xin Guohua). The other focus is the contemporary artist's utilization and transformation of China's cultural heritage from without. Experimenting with installation, performance, photography, and video, and adopting postmodern strategies of deconstruction, appropriation, and bricolage, these artists defy the framework of Guohua and assimilate Chinese elements into dynamic interactions between the local and the global. Wu Hung, Professor, Department of Art History, University of Chicago, tried to define three particular strategies that contemporary Chinese artists have developed to negotiate with traditions. He called them Distilling Materiality, Translating Visuality, and Refiguration.

With the development of art globalization and diversification, Chinese contemporary ink painting art has gradually lost its traditional solitary ideological background, and both styles and concepts have presented a diversified situation. This article briefly discusses the current situation of contemporary cultural context to show that the expansion and innovation of ink and wash language changes according to the needs of art and the needs of the times. It further shows that no matter how the ink language is changed by artists in its medium and expression in the contemporary, its ink spirit exists in contemporary artworks[1]. From the cultural background of the artistic spirit, the way of transformation, the construction of aesthetic ideas, and the modern

turn of literati ink language, this paper expounds the morphological language of the development of Chinese contemporary ink painting. In general terms, this study will discuss the cultural characteristics of new ink language and the motivation of language transformation, and as well as the new problems in the process of the transition of new ink painting language.

2. Genre of Chinese Ink Art

2.1. Brush and Ink (Bi-Mo)

In the late 1980s, traditional ink painting founded on the aesthetics of “Brush-and-Ink (Bimo) and new trends in art” conflicted in mainland China; this was the subject of debates. In these circumstances the artwork of such - traditional ink painters as Huang Binhong, Qi Baishi (1863-1957), and Pan Tianshuo (1897-1971) was revived and re-debated. The contemporary critic Jia Fang zhou observed in 1993: Brush-and-ink (Bimo) is not only one of the essential ideas of Huang Binhong’s interpretation of the painting, but it is also the fundamental of his art with this significant idea in mind, his art was free of numerous layers, becoming simple and clear, Huang Binhong not only has well-known for his own position in the art world but also has prominent the tradition of literati painting to the new elevation of pure art.,The brush-and-ink painting,there is interesting anxiety between the spiritual and historical; the historical and contemporary.

2.2 Modern Ink Art

Modern ink painting is an eye-catching artistic phenomenon in Chinese painting since the rise of the 85 Art Wave. Modern ink painting is based on the changes in traditional techniques and concepts of ink art. It has already made many breakthroughs in the language of technique. Lin Fengmian’s Western painting method, Zhang Daqian’s splashing color method, Liu Guosong’s thin paper texture processing method, Zhou Yuhua’s print paper retreat method, Cheng Zhongchen’s water addition method, etc. The most important was new technology to pay attention to the methods of new ways of art. Since the 1980s, the modernization of ink art has become a common concern of some inspirational and innovative artists. The creation of modern ink paintings began in the early 1980s and it was active in the mid-to-late 1990s. Nowadays, it has become a trend that cannot be ignored in the field of Chinese painting.

From the classification point of view, modern ink can be roughly divided into four categories. *First* is expressive ink, it’s a kind of modern ink art form with expressionism style. *Second*:The new method and concepts are explored, since the emergence of - new literati painting, has been accompanied by the avant-garde.*Third*: urban ink, the overall style of urban ink reflects the

attempt to explain the artist's perception of urban culture and life, therefore, urban ink is still to reflect modern life, show the modern spirit for the purpose. *Fourth*: is experimental ink. It abandoned the heavy mechanism of brush, ink and traditional aesthetic taste changed the connection with the traditional ink spirit, and tried to establish the modern art system which is different from traditional ink and realistic ink. It is mainly influenced by Western modern and post-modern art.

2.3 Contemporary Ink Art

Chinese contemporary ink painting is a new artistic concept based on the contemporary development of traditional Chinese painting. The meaning of contemporary ink and wash has two meanings conceptually: *First*, refers to the contemporary category of its time, specifically, it refers to our contemporary era background under different past contemporary social, economic, technological and cultural development states; *Second*, it refers to the expressive elements of ink and wash, which is the most basic ink and wash material and form in traditional Chinese painting. Among them, there are not only the elements of traditional inheritance but also the cultural fashion and orientation of the current era. The involvement of traditional art in the field of contemporary art has played a positive role in the development and meaning of the possibility of contemporary art, and may also change some traditional views since the cultural movement [2]. Contemporary ink painting has always been regarded as an apostate in traditional Chinese painting. Obviously, they have broken the formula of traditional ink painting, but have not yet established their own discourse system, so they are extremely inaccessible and in a marginalized zone.

2.4 Expressive Ink Art

Chinese ink art technique has always paid attention to the charm of brush and ink, image modeling, emotion is more noticeable to the sense of expression and personal style of communication. Thus, to some level, there is a certain connection between Chinese ink art and Western modern expressionism, and these two are more likely to connect with each other in artistic language and painting ideas. The expressive forms and artistic activities of traditional ink painting share clear connections with Western expressionism: the liberty of brushwork, the expression of character, the purification of emotion, the figuration of imagery. It is for this reason that, in the mid-1980s, a group of artists appropriated the ideas of Western expressionism to reformation traditional ink painting. Li Shinan (b.1940) and Li Jin (b.1958) are two prominent

artists of the expressionist ink painting of the mid-1980s. Li Xiaoxuan and Wang Yanping, in particular, combined their own emotions, everyday experience, and urban themes in the totality of their work, which often surprises its audience.

2.5 Abstract Ink Art

Abstract ink, it is an art style with special significance that originated in the 1960s, established in the 1985 New Wave Art Period, and grew up in the field of Chinese painting in the 1990s. Strictly speaking, it is not a school or a style. It is a trend of thought that influences and even change the fate of Chinese painting. In terms of specific creative styles, abstract ink painting presents a diversified art form, which can be roughly divided into three types expressive abstract ink painting centered on spiritual exploration and self-expression; and language experiment and form innovation Media abstract ink and wash; conceptual abstract ink and wash guided by artistic methods such as behavior and installation. The development of Chinese abstract art in the late 20th century benefited from the active and contentious art theories, especially due to Wu Guanzhong's research and vigorous advocacy of "formal beauty" and "abstract beauty" in the 1980s. Entering the 21st century, the development of abstract art in China has ushered in a new wave of trends. First, a group of artists, mainly artists who studied and lived in Germany, they all returned from abroad and has brought a vibrant new atmosphere such as Xu Jiang, Tan Ping, Ma Lu, Zhou Chunya, Yang Jinsong, MengLuding, Yin Qi, Su Xiaobai, Liu Yonggang, Zhang Guolong, Ma Shuqing, Zhu Jinshi, Huang Gonghang, etc.

2.6 Conceptual Ink Art

Conceptual art is an art movement created on the view that idea or concept is the essence of art. Art doesn't even have to take on a physical form. It can be something the artist says or does or a document of the artist's thinking. Chinese contemporary ink art since the 1990s has experienced exceptional artistic transformation, with a multidimensional development of Chinese ink painting on the course to modernization [3]. The conceptual beginning and use of contemporary arts represent a breakthrough in the current Chinese painting world, reflecting the influence of the incorporation of contemporary Western art into China, and a Chinese domestic artistic aspiration for an innovative contemporary expression, while also showing the developing tendency of Chinese ink painting reaching out to the world. The artist Zhang Yu is one of the significant representatives of Chinese contemporary ink painting art. In the early 1980s, artists started to use

ink and wash as a beginning point for artistic creation. In the early 1990s, the art of fingerprint was formed.

2.7 Urban Ink Art

The term “Urban” means from the city which is originated from the Latin word urbanus. The creation of modern urban ink painting, in a sense, it is a challenge to the traditional ink language, but also an opportunity for modernization. Urban ink and wash has opened up our vision and provided us with a possibility to lead us to extend our influence into a broader field, to create a new concept and a new form that is different from the traditional one and the pattern of the old aesthetic standard. This is an era of urbanization, people must be concerned about how the artists of our era know and express our times, and artists should also pay attention to the cities in which they live and incorporate them into their own brush and style. Shi Tao once said that - brush and ink should be contemporary, in fact, he also said that Chinese painting should be contemporary. The change of the objects of Chinese painting from landscape to city will certainly cause a revolution in painting, which may bring a great change in Chinese painting or ink painting.

2.8 Experimental Ink Art

Experimental ink and wash is a cultural phenomenon and painting exploration movement that emerged in the 1980s and 1990s and will continue, develop, and influence. Experimental ink and wash is a form, but what kind of form is it? Some people think that experimental ink and wash are abstract ink and wash; others think that experimental ink and wash are modern ink and wash, which should include representational and expressive concrete ink. For a long time, artists only cared about their own creative forms and the self in their creations. As for others, they didn't care much about their creations [4]. Achievement of “experimental ink and wash” is that it has provided us with much meaningful ink and wash texts over the years, allowing us to see much unprecedented contemporary ink and wash expressions with distinct and unique artistic personalities. These contemporary ink artworks, which are based on Chinese contemporary real life and get inspiration from it, and at the same time can draw nourishment from the local and national cultural traditions, neither revert to the ancients nor copy aboard.

3. Source of New Ink Art

3.1 Basic Concept of New Ink Art

Ink painting is also called freehand painting, and it is divided into three periods from its birth to the present. The *first period* is the classical ink era. From ancient times to modern times, it is

characterized by uncertain and flat images. Therefore, it can also be called the unclear image era. The *second stage* is the modern era of ink painting. Since the Republic of China, Chinese painting has accepted the aesthetics of Western painting, and the Xu Jiang art education system has been established. It attempts to express accurate light, shade, structure, and hue. The comprehensive gradation and the expression of hue are simplifying, so it can also be called the era of generalized imagery. The *third period* is the new ink painting age, and the corresponding school is called the new ink painting School. It uses compound strokes as technical features and a particular color tone as its artistic image features, so it can also be called the era of precise imagery. New Chinese ink painting School of Li Shaobai Faqi, it has just entered a stage of rapid development. The new ink art doesn't exactly refer to a certain style or type of ink painting, nor does it merely refer to the ink image generated by the Western contemporary art and formed by the artist's concept of ink painting. The new ink art is a minimal status of contemporary ink artexpression, which encloses new ink media, ink concept, ink expression, and new ink concept as well as non-frame ink behavior. In the 1980s, new ink art emerged, in the mid-to-late 1990s, the development of new ink art developed through limitless of the traditional art and historical period. From the beginning, it was not recognized by the public until it was gradually accepted until it began to appear in various parts of the country [5].

3.2 Causes of New Ink Art

Cultural Revolution: After the Reform and Opening-up, the ultimate of the old disorder has been basically broken, the introduction of Western culture has also lifted the ideological encloses of people who have been confined by outdated culture for many years, and many new ideas, in the West have been driving into the country, bringing many books and picture albums to the domestic art world to introduce international modern art exhibitions and affected most of the ink artists, they endeavor to innovate the artists began to seek the path of innovation in ink art, seeking the path to the revival of Chinese painting. The transformation of social and cultural context, combined with the influence of Western modern art, is the beginning and disclosing of the new ink art in such a big background.

Personal Exploration of the Subject: In artistic creation activities, artists are producers and creators of works of art. First of all, the creation of a work of art cannot be separated from the intuitive feeling, imagination, and thinking of the artistic creation, through the aesthetic object, and the aesthetic characteristics of the works of art cannot be separated from the artistic creator's

experience, thinking, and exploration of social life. Therefore, combined with the new ink artists, whether it is external conditions of social life or internal reasons for the artist's main psychology will have a certain impact on his creative works of art.

Impact of Urban Culture: The rapid development of urbanization has brought advanced creative media to ink art, and the new ink artists have applied comprehensive materials and new forms of ink language together, which is to confirm that the urban cultural background provides a realistic soil for the inspiration of the artist's main body, as well as a revolution against the background of urban cultural life, is also out of a wake-up call for yourself not to lose yourself on the road to future creation. Urban social life experience is an external aspect of artist's life experience, here we discuss the changes of new ink artist's life experience in urban culture, the following mainly analyzes the life experience of artists in urban cultural background, and we will analyze the life experience of an artist's works.

4. Philosophy and Aesthetics of New Ink Art

New ink art belongs to the category of the post-philosophical field. Including artists are reflecting on the good and bad consequences brought to humanity in the industrial age. The new nature of post-philosophy has become a consensus in recent years. It emphasizes the harmony between man and nature. They talk about the unity of people and the world, or the unity of subject and object, and the Chinese Taoist philosophy is about the unity of heaven and man. The basic point of the post-philosophical theory is to transcend the contradiction between the subject and the object and make the subject and the object connect to achieve a high degree of integration and harmony between man and nature. Philosophers from all over the world re-understand Daoist and Zen thought because the thought of the unity of man and nature talked about by Taoism should be the ideological pursuit of human beings. Laozi's exploration of beauty destitute through the relationship between individual psychological desire and social ethics established by Confucianism. He believed that beauty is in the Tao, truth and goodness are unified in the Tao. In view of human alienation and distorted human nature, Zhuangzi pointed out that the way out of life is Obedience, obeying and returning to the natural nature of human beings so that individual life transcends all the limitations of reality and reaches the natural realm[6]. This supreme ideological realm should be integrated into contemporary works by thoughtful artists in order to promote Taoist thought.

Both Western land art and Japanese materialistic art are still pursuing the first nature. The so-called first is the nature in which people see and live. The art of materialism appeared in 1968, at which time Japan was in the prime of the world's second-largest economy after World War II. Modern philosophy once called nature without human transformation the first nature, called nature after human transformation the second nature, and generally called the natural object. Natural objects refer to things and phenomena in nature, including naturally occurring natural objects and man-made natural objects formed by human production practices. The former is called the first nature and the latter is called the second nature. However, post-philosophy has revised the concept of modern philosophy. It believes that the second nature is a concept produced in the field of philosophy and art. The first nature cannot be separated from the second nature. Traditional painting is -representing objectivity, modern art is representing subjectivity, and the main purpose of post-modern art is representing nature and representing the true. How to -present nature and recreate -second nature is itself contrary to the art form of traditional painting and the general form and idea of modern art creation. Second nature is an important concept in the field of aesthetics and literary studies. Second nature borrows a term used in Western aesthetics. The second nature we are talking about here the artistic spirit of Zhuangzi.

5. Ink is a Concept, Not a Medium

"...Ink art is really a concept, not just a medium". Maxwell K. Hearn -Ink art is really a concept, not just a medium, I realized that ink art is really a concept, not just a medium, that ink art can represent a traditional way of painting, either calligraphy landscape, and even abstract art, photograph or video art. The format often takes the form of a handscroll; it may appear like a traditional painting but simply with the new technology. So, I thought just because its new technology doesn't mean it doesn't relate to tradition. The monochrome pallet of the photographs still resonates with traditional ink painting. So, ink, whether it's from an inkjet printer or from a brush is still ink. Artists developing ink painting or art have moved into an experimental mode, evolving from regular trends to contemporary aesthetics. Ink art signifies an aesthetic sensibility, as it is more than an artistic medium. His large argument is that inside the history of art and calligraphy, the typical ink arts exist examples of revival, reference, and transformation situated on surviving gratitude of the past. In his words, the earlier is present in Chinese art. Here, Hearn tried to explain a new perspective of Chinese contemporary ink art, he acknowledged that ink just not only an ordinary medium, but it can also be the philosophy of modern time[7].

6. Categorization of the Artist and Style

“Chinese painting now” essay written by Jason C. Kuo, he categorized the artist into three major parts according to medium, concept, philosophy such as:

6.1. Concept and Medium

Neo-Traditionalists(could be also called neo-Classicists) are artists who still trust on brushwork and ink washes or color for expression; they include: Chan Ky-Yut, Dou Liangyu, Fang Jun, Gao Xingjian, Ho HuaiShuo, JiaYoufu, Li Huayi, Li Jin, Tang Guo, Tong Yang Tze, Li Xiaoxuan, Li Xubai, Liu Dan, Liu Qinghe, Lo Ching, Wang Jianan, Wu Yi, Xu Lei, Yang Yanping, Yu Peng, Yuan Jai, Zeng Shanqing, Zeng Xiaojun, and Zhu Daoping.

Synthesizers are artists who use ink as well as other media (such as acrylic) and combine Chinese and non-Chinese styles while not trusting exclusively on brushwork and ink washes and traditional color as their means of expression, these are included: Huang Yong Ping, Huang Zhiyang, Kan Tai Keung, Fay Ku, ChunYiLee, Leung Kui Ting, Li Jun, Liang Quan, Liu Kuo-Sung, Liu Wei, Lu Hao, Miao Xiaochun, Pan Hsin-Hua, Qin Feng, QiuDeshu, QiuJie, Wang Dongling, Wang Jinsong, Wei Ligang, Wei Dong, Wucius Wong, Zhang Dawo, Zhang Chun Hong, Zhang Huan, and Zhang Yu.

Interrogators are artists in whose works the cultural and historical meanings of ink as a medium are questioned and even challenged, and they explore ink’s physical and chemical features: hen Guangwu, GuGan, WendaGu, QiuZhijie, Wang Tiande, Wei Qingji, Xu Bing, Yang Jiechang, and You Si.

6.2 Style Based

Reconstruction of the traditional aesthetics of Brush-and- ink (Bimo):Fang Jun, Ho Huai-Shuo, Leung Kui Ting, Li Huayi, Li Xubai, Liu Dan, Liu Kuosung, Lo Ching, Tong Yangtze, Wang Dongling, Wang Jianan, Wang Jinsong, Wucius Wong, Yu Peng, Zeng Shanqing, Zeng Xiaojun, Yang Yanping, Zhang Chun Hong.

Abstraction:Chan Kyyut, KanTaikeung, Liang Quan, Liu Kuosung, Gao Xingjian, GuGan, Qin Feng, Tang Guo, Wang Tiande, Wei Ligang, Xu Bing, You Si, Zhang Dawo.

New Expressionism:GuGan, Lei Miao, Li Jin, Li Jun, Liu Qinghe, Li Xiaoxuan, Liu Wei, Wang Dongling, Wang Jinsong, Zhu Daoping, You Si.

*Monumental Landscapes and Constructed Cosmos:*JiaYoufu, WendaGu, Liu Kuo Sung, QiuDeshu, Yang Jiechang, Zhang Yu.

*The Decorative and Blue-and-Green Traditions Regenerated:*Yuan Jai, Pan Hsing-Hua, Fay Ku, Xu Lei.

*Ink as Medium:*Chen Guangwu, WendaGu, Liang Quan, Qin Feng, QiuZhijie, Wang Tiande, Yang Jiechang.

*Social Commentary:*CaiGuangbin, Dou Liangyu, Huang Yong Ping, Huang Zhiyang, Chun-Yi Lee, Li Jin, Liang Quan, Lu Hao, Miao Xiaochun, QiuZhijie, QiuJie, Wei Dong, Wei Qingji, Wu Yi, Xu Bing, Zhang Chun Hong, Zhang Huan

7. Future of Ink Art

Over the past three decades, China has faced philosophical socioeconomic modifications that have encouraged calls to reexamine, review, and redefine the nation's identity. In Chinese contemporary art, ink painting is a problem, as a symptom, or it will become more and clearer in the present time because through ink art we can better understand the problems of contemporary Chinese art adaptation and experiments with or without ink. Ink art may better respond to the three types of problems in contemporary Chinese art. *First*, what kind of cultural value can be accepted by the world in the characteristics of Chinese contemporary art? Here, ink painting may serve as a direction for us to reflect on the cultural crisis of the contemporary world. *Second*, how should modern ink-and-wash inks continue to develop over time? *Third*, ink is just only a material. The relevant question in today's China is whether the country's separate traditions and values can continue to play a role in its development. The future of China cannot be predicted, yet the psychology of renovate, Modification, Transformation that pervades the everyday lives of the Chinese permits for a multitude of possibilities. Only in the recreation of these new potentialities will China be able to shape its distinctive culture.

Conclusion

The 20th century is a century in which Chinese ink painting has undergone many morphological transformations and changes. Every major social change and every important ideological movement has had a philosophical impact on the transformation of ink painting. In the past century, ink painting has undergone changes in form. In the transformation of a century, ink painting has always used the West as the frame of reference, or even the Western model. The

First conversion was in the context of the May Fourth New Culture Movement. The *Second* change and transformation of ink art took place in the 1980s when reform and opening-up were implemented. Chinese contemporary ink painting is based on the heritage of traditional Chinese painting and developed a concept of art with the characteristics of the times. The “Contemporary ink painting” contains two meanings: *First* is the contemporary category in time, specifically, it is our contemporary background that is different from the past social, economic, technological and cultural development; and the *Second*, It refers to the expression elements of ink painting, which is the most basic ink painting material and form in traditional Chinese painting. There are both elements of traditional inheritance and the cultural style and orientation of the current era.

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